

Bridging mathematics students and the challenges of their learning disabilities

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Students without recognized levels of academic numeracy and literacy for university entrance are often diverted into a six-to-twelve month bridging or foundation programme where they must pass a mathematics course. However, a small number have struggled to learn mathematics from their earliest schooling and they again find themselves in an uncomfortably similar position. The students have known or unknown mathematical learning disabilities (MLDs) which may account for their own perceived lack of progress in mathematics, their frustrations and anxiety. An aim of the study is to find out how the mathematical learning needs of these students at a few New Zealand universities are being supported. In the early stages of this doctoral project, students with MLDs who failed at bridging mathematics share their experiences.

Introduction

Students entering degree programmes are expected to have sufficient levels of academic numeracy (and literacy) before being accepted. Most entrants arrive with Year 12 and 13 mathematics credits from the National Certificate of Educational Achievement (NCEA) as evidence of their readiness for university degree studies. Students without these levels and credits are often diverted into bridging, pre-degree or foundation programmes which may take from six months to a year to complete. Benseman and Russ (2003, p. 45) define bridging (or foundation) programmes as providing learners with “the requisite academic skills that will enable them to enrol in other tertiary programmes to which they would not otherwise have been able to gain entry.” At one of the participant universities, each student on a bridging programme must pass at least one mathematics course to satisfy academic numeracy requirements. However, a small proportion of students on the programme have struggled to learn mathematics from their earliest educational experiences and often find themselves in an uncomfortably familiar situation when they must again face learning mathematics.

Some entrants have known or unknown mathematics learning disabilities (MLDs) which may account for their perceived lack of traction when learning mathematics, and the resultant frustrations and anxieties. This is exacerbated for those who fail their first semester bridging mathematics course, then find themselves once again having to take the same course in semester two. MLDs are described as “cognitive *deficits* in a student’s processing of numerical information that lead to persistent and pervasive difficulties with mathematics”

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(Lewis, 2017, p. 321, original italics). However, labelling with a 'deficit' assumes that people without MLDs somehow occupy the high ground of normality while the diversity among human beings and their abilities is overlooked, and what mathematics they are actually being asked to do.

Positioning students with LDs is tenuous at best when describing what they contend with as some kind of medical condition and ignores their social identities (Lambert, 2018) and their working and learning environments. In terms of framing this study, Lambert's and Tan's (2017) disability studies in mathematics education (DSME) supports the privileging of student stories about learning and their reflections about the systemic trials they have encountered. Accordingly, the early part of this doctoral study documents some voices of students with MLDs who have shared their mathematical learning experiences, particularly those with MLDs who failed the bridging mathematics course in their first semester then went on to repeat the same course in their second semester to try to meet a challenging academic numeracy target.

Motivation for the study

The initial motivation for the study came from observing students' struggles in the years prior to the second semester repeat course being offered. Before 2015, even though students had failed the mathematics course in their first semester, they were still promoted into a more conceptually demanding second semester course to meet their academic numeracy requirements in the same calendar year. It is likely that these struggling mathematics students were given an even deeper hole within which to flounder and unsurprisingly several dropped out. In the 2011 cohort for instance, of the seventeen students who achieved D grades or less in the first semester course, and who then were invited to take the second semester course, seven recorded yet another D grade while the other ten finished with a Did Not Sit result.

With the repeat class being offered from 2015, although the same mathematical hurdles are still in place for failing students, the material is relatively recent. With there being a five-week mid-year break between the courses, these students have possibly maintained some learning momentum depending on what they understood in the first run. This understanding, however, is not always evident since several students with experiences of learning disabilities have inconsistencies in some fundamental mathematical ideas with which they were perhaps not supported through in their earlier learning. Their long histories of frustration with mathematics and the stories of their endurance provide a second motivation for this interpretative study.

Method

A small initial sample (n=7) of bridging mathematics students from a university bridging programme who failed their first semester maths course and then were asked to repeat it, were approached by a programme administrator to take part in an interview with the author. The group of student participants was spread across several cohort years from a large local

university. The bridging programme they were on typically had a year-long schedule of eight papers with at least one being mathematical. With the COVID-19 situation, three participants chose to be interviewed via Zoom while the others opted for a face-to-face setting while the city was between lockdowns. In a semi-structured interview setting, participants responded to a set of questions about their previous experiences when learning mathematics at school and their transition to university bridging mathematics. The author also took field notes during some of the conversations and two participants wrote to aid their explanations. The Zoom audio-recording function enabled transcribing, before each transcript was returned to the participant for checking. Some preliminary themes emerged from the interviews and several of these are discussed in the next section.

Preliminary findings

There is not room to include all of the preliminary themes so only a few key participant themes that recur have been discussed below. Most of the learners recounted struggles with learning mathematics from their primary schooling. Julia explained how her ADHD impacted on how she was treated by teachers.

I was always labelled as the problem kid, and a little too difficult to deal with. And I think a lot of the time, especially in primary school, if I was disrupting, or I wasn't paying attention, they'd think that I ... I don't know, they'd just pop me off to something like they wouldn't bother with trying to teach me and actually sit me down.

Often other family members or tutors would be engaged for support, but this assistance with mathematics would sometimes backfire. Sarah's mother is a teacher and they would often work side by side after school, but Sarah's memories were far from fond.

We always did our homework together and that's when you know we she has a very short attention. I have a very short attention span. She y ... she's very impatient. So, you know, we always ended up fighting and I always ended up crying. And it was just, yeah. I think that's probably how it started. Just associating maths words with crying and anxiety.

Another recurring theme was how just about every participant ended up in the lowest stream in secondary school. So not only was there the struggle to understand mathematical concepts, but there was what could also be described as the twin losses of face by being withdrawn from their peers and shifted into learning mathematics alongside a younger cohort.

After leaving school some went to work before entertaining the idea of returning to studies at university. They often worked in poorly paid jobs to support themselves during or between school and university. Gracie was one of the earlier work starters and describes how exhausted she would be in classes, which also perhaps contributed to her learning struggles:

Even during school ... I started working when I was about 14. Um I was looking everywhere so I started working at Maccas ... and then in the end a lot of fast food places. And so even when I came to University I was still working. So it was pretty hard to keep up and I that's why I was like (someone would ask) did you go to that lesson? I was tired all the time ...

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Drawing on fundamental mathematics remains a challenge for some. Two participants who work in hospitality separately described how the need for speed and accuracy when cashing up the register or balancing the electronic or credit card transactions at the end of their shifts made them feel inadequate beside other staff members who could be 'trusted' to complete the task. While there was no lack of either wanting to be able to manage those tasks by themselves, the amount of time they would need to deliberately check and recheck the money tallies was, after an unspecified period of time, either not offered them, or they ended up not volunteering for it altogether.

There is a lingering question about what actually happens when these learners are trying to understand mathematics. Julia describes a kind of 'brain fog' enveloping her when confronted with learning, and her exasperation with combatting this.

So cognitively, since I already struggle to focus. I mean, obviously, with years of practice, I've become better at that but my brain fog is not great. It's just like your brain doesn't work properly. It almost feels like your brain half shuts down. You're very slow to think; things that should come quickly to you that should be basic, don't. Just legitimately feels like your brain's kind of shut down and given up and it's very frustrating because you are aware of it and you try to force yourself ...

Participants explained how they had neither the confidence nor the wherewithal to develop authority in mathematical learning, specifically the concepts presented in any mathematics courses. In earlier schooling they would often find themselves being compared to others who were adjudged to be more capable, perhaps reinforcing the negative mould that was never far away from them with regard to this subject.

Looking ahead

Two other universities are being invited into the study. Later interviews will employ focus groups with university bridging mathematics teachers and Disability Support Services staff. It is hoped that their perspectives will provide institutional data with what is being done to support these students.

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